

“AN ANALYSIS OF WORKING OF PAYTM AS A FINTECH COMPANY”**Authors****DR. PREETI YADAV,**

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Abstract

Financial technology (Fintech) defines digital technology that aims to enhance and automate financial services distribution and use. The concept was initially applied to the technologies employed in the back-end of existing financial organizations' networks as fintech startups originated in the 21st century. The Indian Fintech industry ecosystem sees a wide range of subsegments, including Payments, Lending, Wealth Technology (WealthTech), Personal Finance Management, Insurance Technology (InsurTech), Regulation Technology (RegTech), etc. The Fintech sector in India has seen funding of \$8.53 Bn (in 278 deals) in FY22. As of March 2022, India's Unified Payments Interface (UPI) has seen the participation of 313 banks and has recorded 5.4 Bn monthly transactions worth over \$128 Bn. As of April 2022, India has 16 Fintech companies, which have gained 'Unicorn Status' with a valuation of over \$1 bn. The present study has been undertaken to analyse the growth of fintech companies in India with special reference to Paytm. The paper is not confined to any particular area; on the other hand, it is applicable to the whole of India. The paper highlights the demand for fintech companies in India. It analysis the working of Paytm as a fintech company. The paper highlights the challenges faced by fintech companies and present suggestions for the growth of fintech companies in India. The paper concludes with the fact that fintech should work on these services where other financial services are not up to the mark. Fast services, easy accessibility and cheap service are the major factors contributing to use of FinTech by customers.

Keywords: Fintech, startups, technology, financial, UPI

INTRODUCTION

Fintech also known as Financial Technology means a firm or an organization that merge the upcoming and innovative technological trends in order to provide better financial services or solutions to its clients in the form of digital payments and transactions. India, after COVID-19 era has molded itself into an economy which is digitally equipped private fintech startups and fintech companies are being promoted based on their service quality. In the present scenario, individuals are inclined towards the idea of digital payments which leads to the success of such fintech companies in India.

Fintech startups brought a substantial change in the Indian economy and major changes in making payments. The payment system has changed the way people conduct business. Today the majority of the literate people have mobile banking in their phones, which helps them to do all their banking transactions at their fingertips from the comfort of their homes or any other place.

The ban of 500 and 1000 banknotes in November 2016 by the Indian Government along with the outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic augmented a digital payment drive and accelerated the rise of fintech companies. Since then, the digital payment market is ever-growing in India, the country is still struggling to achieve better financial inclusion. This is an issue that comes hand in hand with the alarmingly high illiteracy rate in India which is around 70%.

India is amongst the fastest growing Fintech markets in the world and there are 6,636 FinTech startups in India. Indian FinTech industry's market size is \$31 Bn in 2021 and is estimated at \$ 150 Bn by 2025. The Fintech transaction value size is set to grow from US\$ 66 Bn in 2019 to US\$ 138 Bn in 2023, at a CAGR of 20%. The Indian Fintech industry ecosystem sees a wide range of subsegments, including Payments, Lending, Wealth Technology (WealthTech), Personal Finance Management, Insurance Technology (InsurTech), Regulation Technology (RegTech), etc. The Fintech sector in India has seen funding of \$8.53 Bn (in 278 deals) in FY22. As of March 2022, India's Unified Payments Interface (UPI) has seen the participation of 313 banks and has recorded 5.4 Bn monthly transactions worth over \$128 Bn. As of April 2022, India has 16 Fintech companies, which have gained 'Unicorn Status' with a valuation of over \$1 bn.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Technology plays a critical role in the finance industry. Technologies support the bank to reduce operation costs, increase efficiency and performance, and reduce credit risks. Besides that, the technologies facilitate the bank to connect and maintain relationships with customers (Cheng & Qu, 2020; Lee & Shin, 2018; Goldstein et al., 2019; Thakor, 2020). With the rise of technologies in the finance industry, a new kind of company has been formulated; it is the fintech company. The technology platform facilitates the fintech company to provide financial products with the same features as banking products. Additionally, the fintech company also provides new products (e.g., cryptocurrencies). New products are noticed by younger generations (e.g., millennials generations) (Junger & Mietzner, 2020; Pu et al., 2021).

The fintech field is an emerging field (Goldstein et al., 2019; Haddad & Hornuf, 2019; Zavolokina et al., 2016). The debates about fintech are going on, and it is an exciting topic for scholars.

According to Lee and Shin (2018), in the 1990s, the internet and the world wide web had changed the finance industry's face; banking services (savings, transfers), insurance, and stock trading were transacted without the physical location. The application of technologies reduced the price. Since the mid-2000s, the rise of smartphones and new-generation technologies facilitated banking product development. The customer can make a transaction via a personal mobile device. Furthermore, since the post-global financial crisis 2008, the combination of mobile finance, new generation technologies, and social networking, the financial product has been personalized. There is the appearance of new players in the financial market; it is the fintech company. In this stage, we consider that fintech is not only used for indicating the utilization technologies of the conventional bank but also the new players.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The present study has been undertaken to analyze the growth of fintech companies in India with special reference to Paytm. The paper is not confined to any particular area; on the other hand, it is applicable to the whole of India. However, the opinion of finance experts has been taken about the growth of fintech companies. Their views have been incorporated into this paper. The paper also takes the references of various articles written by various experts on the growth of fintech companies and Paytm.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of the study entitled “The growth of Fintech Companies in India- A Case Study of Paytm” are mentioned herein below:

- To highlight the demand for fintech companies in India;
- To analyse the working of Paytm as a fintech company;
- To highlight the challenges faced by fintech companies;
- To present suggestions for the growth of fintech companies in India.

FINTECH STARTUPS AND FINTECH COMPANIES IN INDIA

The important fintech startups and companies are mentioned herein below:

- 1) **Paytm:** Paytm is India's leading financial services company that specializes in digital payment systems, e-commerce and finance. It won the Outstanding Startup of the Year Award at Forbes Leadership Awards in 2016.
- 2) **PhonePe:** PhonePe, based in Bangalore, is another one of India's leading fintech startups that has been able to soar to heights despite the cut-throat competition in the niche. It is an e-commerce payment system & digital wallet company that was founded back in December 2015. The platform is available in over 11 Indian languages and can be used by individuals to transfer money, recharge, pay bills, shop online, and buy from local vendors.
- 3) **Razorpay:** Razorpay is a platform that enables businesses to accept, process, and disburse payments with its product suite. It gives access to all payment modes including credit cards, debit cards, net banking, UPI, and popular wallets.
- 4) **Pine Labs:** Pine Labs is an Indian merchant platform company that provides financing and last-mile retail transaction technology. Founded in 1998, it now has more than 70,000 retailers across India, including major retail outlets such as Mark's and Spencer's Retail, Pantaloons, Shoppers Stop and Westside.
- 5) **MobiKwik:** Launched in 2009, MobiKwik is another large digital payment and wallet company that allows users to carry transactions on multiple platforms from the MobiKwik account on their phones. MobiKwik has registered a 90% growth in monthly active users in FY 2019, where it was also ranked as the second-largest platform for merchant payments. The fintech India firm has originated over 350k entirely digital loans with a loan book standing at \$24 million.
- 6) **Groww:** Groww is an online investment platform that allows investors to invest in mutual funds and stocks. It provides an objective evaluation of mutual funds.
- 7) **BharatPe:** BharatPe is a fintech company that caters to small merchants and kirana store owners of India. The company offers a range of fintech products including

interoperable QR codes for UPI payments, Bharat Swipe (POS machine) for card acceptance, and small business financing. Moreover, It recently announced that it aims to facilitate a loan book of \$300 Million via postpe in the first 12 months for its lending partners.

- 8) **Policybazaar:** Policybazaar is India's largest insurance aggregator. It provides a digital platform – website and app – where users compare financial services from major insurance companies. It provides several types of insurance plans like life insurance, health insurance, motor insurance, travel insurance as well as group plans.
- 9) **Freecharge:** The Gurugram-based fintech company was launched in August 2010 by Kunal Shah and Sandeep Tandon. Freecharge allows its users to pay utility bills, pay Landline bills or recharge Mobile, Broadband, DTH, and Metro cards through its platform. The platform also provides savings, payments, insurance, and lending services to its users.
- 10) **CRED:** CRED is a reward-based credit card bill payment platform; its main feature is allowing users to make credit card payments through its app for which they get rewarded. In addition, CRED allows users to make house rent payments and offers short-term credit lines. CRED has become the youngest Indian startup to be valued at \$2 billion or higher.
- 11) **Digit Insurance:** Digit Insurance is an Indian start-up insurtech that focuses on selling insurance online.
- 12) **CoinSwitch:** CoinSwitch is an Indian cryptocurrency exchange platform where users can put and call cryptocurrencies such as Bitcoin, Ethereum, Ripple etc. with the best rate.
- 13) **Zeta:** Zeta is a banking tech company that provides an Omni Stack comprising modern credit and debit processing, BNPL, core banking, and mobile experiences. It caters to banks and fintechs globally.
- 14) **ChargeBee Technologies:** Chargebee is a SaaS product company. It is a recurring billing and subscription management tool that helps SaaS and SaaS-like businesses streamline Revenue Operations.
- 15) **CoinDCX:** Coin DCX specializes in crypto-enabled financial services. It aims to provide a user-friendly experience where users can access a wide range of financial products and services backed by industry-leading security processes and insurance protection.

- 16) **Acko:** Acko offers an online insurance policy provided through its digital platform. The company has various products and opportunities in main pillars in insurance such as personalized insurance products based on user consumption behaviors.

BUSINESS MODELS ADOPTED BY FINTECH COMPANIES IN INDIA

The fintech companies in India adopted the following models in order to cater to the needs of the customers:

- Introduction of digital wallets into the ecosystem
- Digital insurance for health, travel, etc.
- Digital banking solutions simplifying banking
- Peer-to-Peer lending systems making credit reliable
- Alternative credit scoring allowing individuals to make better lending decisions

KEY DRIVERS FOR FINTECH COMPANIES IN INDIA

The key drivers for the growth of fintech companies in India are mentioned herein below:

- 1) **Increased funding:** A substantial increase in investments from venture capital, private equity and institutional investment has encouraged the rise of FinTech startups.
- 2) **Government initiatives and Regulators:** Government initiatives like Jan Dhan Yojana, Digital India Programme, Startup India, etc. have played a vital role in encouraging the growth of startups. Startup India, for example, has enabled an online platform-based solution for entrepreneurs to safeguard their intellectual property (IP) and it has offered the startups some exemptions from taxes under certain eligibility criteria. The regulations developed by the RBI, IRDAI and SEBI has ensured increased accountability and the uninterrupted availability of secure and affordable digital financial systems.
- 3) **International Collaboration:** Startup India has enabled collaboration between Indian startup ecosystem and the global startup ecosystem by enabling bridges that provide a soft landing to emerging new startups from the partnering countries. It has helped promoted enthusiasm by fostering knowledge exchange and fund support mechanisms.
- 4) **India Stack:** India stack is a set of APIs that allows governments, businesses, startups, and developers to utilize a unique and common digital Infrastructure. These open API platforms include Aadhar, UPI, Bharat Bill payments, etc.

- 5) **Innovation in Technology:** New business models are being developed using technologies like Machine learning and Artificial Intelligence.
- 6) **Increase in smartphone and internet users:** India has the 2nd highest number of smartphone users globally with numbers around 550-600 million, and 2nd largest Internet user market with over 795 million internet users as of December 2020.

DEMAND FOR FINTECH COMPANIES IN INDIA

Table 1: Demand for Fintech

<i>S. No.</i>	<i>Demand</i>	<i>For</i>	<i>Fintech</i>
1	Consumers	Payments	Online payments OTC payments mobile wallets
		Remittances	Low cost, Fast money transfers (domestic as well as international)
		Savings, Investment, Personal Finance Management	Customized savings and investment plans
2	Businesses	Reach	Ensuring growth and sustenance of small retailers
		Funding	Fast access to various forms of working and investment capital at lower costs
3	Banks and financial institutions	Customer acquisition	Innovative products and services Low cost channels
		Risk Mitigation	Improved credit scoring and risk management

		Financial inclusion	Leveraging technology to expand to underserved markets
4	Government	Benefit payments	DBT Other government benefits
		Bill payments	Bharat bill payment system and other utilities

ANALYSIS OF WORKING OF PAYTM AS A FINTECH COMPANY

Paytm is an Indian MNC specializes in various domains such as digital payment systems, e-commerce, and financial services. Paytm started its inception in Noida. It is currently available in more than 11 Indian languages and provides various offerings like mobile recharges, bill payments, travel, movies, and events bookings as well as in-store payments at grocery stores, fruits and vegetable shops, restaurants, parking, tolls, pharmacies and educational institutions with the Paytm QR Code.

(A) Highlights of Paytm

Table 2: Highlights

Startup Name	Paytm
Sector	Fintech
Parent Organisation	One97 Communications
Establishment Year	2010
Headquarter	Noida (UP)
Founder	Mr. Vijay Shekhar Sharma
Revenue or Turnover	Rs, 1100 Crore (Approx in the year 2021)
Funding	3.5 Billion Dollar
Products	Paytm Wallet Paytm App Paytm Money Paytm Payments Bank Paytm First Games Paytm First Credit Card

	Paytm Insurance
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(B) Establishment of Paytm

In 2000, Vijay Shekhar Sharma established Paytm's parent organization One97 Communications, through taking a loan of Rs 8 lakh. He went on to finally establish the Noida-based Paytm in 2010 as a prepaid mobile and DTH (direct-to-home) recharge platform. But from those humble beginnings, he ended up with a great force Paytm into the country's most valued fintech start-up in less than a decade. Post the launch of the Paytm Wallet in 2014, it became one of the most used digital wallets across India. Over the course of the next few years, Paytm widened its base and expanded into e-commerce through ticket bookings and online deals. It leads the market share in the year 2016 after the government's shock ban on high-value currency notes (Rs500 and Rs1000 Notes) on 8th November 2016 magnified digital payments. A high percentage of people adapt online payments method at that time which will help Paytm to grow rapidly.

After the demonetization in India, "Paytm Karo" became the legendary catchphrase that every Indian got hooked on when it came to online shopping and as well as offline shopping because a Payment facility through QR Code is acceptable in almost every shop or Petrol Pump in the market. In the year 2017, the company became the country's first-ever payments app to surpass the threshold of 100 million downloads. Today Paytm boasts of 1.2 billion monthly transactions (as of March 1, 2021) with over 150 million monthly active users.

(C) Paytm IPO

Paytm was the biggest IPO (Initial Public Offer) offered in the Indian Share Market. Paytm company was listed in the Share Market on 18th November 2021. Its offer surpassed the biggest public offer by Coal India of Rs 15,200 Crores in 2010. Despite making a debut in the Market, Paytm managed to cross the milestone of Rs 1 lakh crore market capitalization. The digital payments firm reached a market cap of Rs 1.19 lakh crore on BSE. The share is listed at Rs 1,955 on BSE, a discount of 9.06% to the issue price. Later, the market cap of the firm fell to Rs 1.10 lakh crore, as the share further dipped 20.47% to Rs 1,704 on BSE. On NSE, the share of Vijay Shekhar Sharma-led company opened at Rs 1,950, a 9.30% discount to the IPO issue price. The share further fell 20.93% to Rs 1,700 on NSE. As on 26.08.2022 the share price close to 762.05

(D) Business Model

Fig 1: Revenue Model of Paytm

Paytm has laid the foundation for the various other digital payment platforms we observe in the Indian nation, as it sets an example from which these companies can observe and imbibe. Initially Paytm limited its focus towards the requirements of the younger population and later on extended its emphasis to incorporate the older Indian population as well.

From being a mere recharge and bill payment platform, the organization has expanded to emerge as an online banking service kind of website that offers a plethora of offers as well as services. The platform is one of the rare payment sites that facilitates 50- 100% cashback in pretty much all the payment transactions undertaken by the user. The application facilitates the customers with an e-wallet feature that allows them to store a section of the amount exclusively for particular transactions. Paytm's platform also facilitates online booking as well as reservation services.

The platform functions as a sort of marketplace that permits users to execute their daily requirements easily. It is also a virtual bank that has been approved by the Reserve Bank of India. The platform has also launched the idea of Digital Gold through which the users can perform online purchasing and selling of gold. They contain an all-time functioning customer service facility that promptly resolves any problems relating to the application.

(E) Paytm Growth

At the start of September 2020, Paytm declared its launch of a subscription service for businesses. Titled 'Paytm Subscriptions', the service aims to allow businesses to gather payments from their users through flexible and easy payment methods like Paytm wallets, cards, or UPI. The Paytm Payments Bank Limited platform announced that its net profit in FY 19-20 escalated to Rs.29.8 Cr from Rs.19.2 Cr in the last year, resulting in an escalation of

55%. As claimed by Paytm on its blog, the platform's FY20 revenue grew to Rs.3,629 Cr with a 40 percent fall in losses in comparison to the previous year.

(F) Analysis of Paytm working

The working of Paytm can be analysed in the following points:

- 1) **Solving problems to create opportunity:** Most people living in India use Paytm, they use it for everything from buying groceries and paying school tuition fees to selecting insurance products and getting loans. The fintech was founded less than a decade ago. Yet, today, more than 7 million merchants across India use its QR code-based mobile payment system. The app has been downloaded more than 100 million times; the number of registered users has jumped from just 11 million in 2014 to more than 420 million today. Revenues soared to US\$480 million in 2018.
- 2) **Looking for the source of the pain:** Paytm's core business has always revolved around payments. But the company sees itself more as a 'problem solver' than a bank or a tech firm. The approach of the company is to identify the pain points for customers and then solve them. The first pain point the company solved for India's consumers was around pre-paid mobile top-ups: Paytm allowed customers to top their accounts up instantly on their phones rather than going to a store, buying a top-up card, and struggling with an extraordinarily long password. That allowed it to build brand awareness and a loyal customer base.
- 3) **Fixing the system:** Another objective of the company was much more ambitious i.e. to make India's payment system more inclusive, more efficient, and more reliable. It was a bold goal. When the company was founded, the vast majority of India's population had no access to formal banking services at all. Those that did have bank accounts often struggled to use the instruments available to them. Less than 2 percent of the population had a credit account. Cash and cheques were the norms. In 2014, the company introduced the Paytm Wallet which allows customers to store money in their virtual wallet through which Indian consumers could now make transactions using digital money.
- 4) **A super-app in the making:** In the last few years, Paytm added dozens of new use cases for its technology. Paytm's mobile payment platform was, for a time, the only payment method accepted by Uber in India. It partnered with a wide range of transport, utility, and entertainment companies to create digital payment systems. And it launched

an e-marketplace where customers can find almost any item or service available in India, often at a discounted rate.

- 5) **Creating markets:** While it may seem as if Paytm is taking on the traditional banking system, it is not. In fact, Paytm is providing a pivotal intersection between India's population and the established banking order. Paytm attempts to bring half a billion unbanked Indian consumers into the formal banking system.
- 6) **Driving customer acquisition:** Yet Paytm's goal is not just to sell products to users. It's also to help users achieve their own goals. That often means helping them establish themselves in the mainstream economy. In a cash economy, small businesses and merchants are often overlooked by traditional banks due to a lack of reliable records and credit history. Paytm helps to solve that pain point by using its technology to create a robust and reliable view of its business users — their cash flows, their customers, their daily balance sheet status, and so on. And they use that view to help the business establish its credit-worthiness.
- 7) **Out of India:** The company has been looking for opportunities to use its technology to address payment opportunities outside of India. The company partnered with Japan's Softbank and Yahoo! Japan to launch a new digital payment system in Japan. When Paytm launched PayPay in Japan, about 87 percent of personal retail transactions were happening with cash. Japan is such a large economy with significant consumer spending. The opportunity to apply the Paytm technology to help solve that problem was obvious. Paytm also sees a significant opportunity in Canada where the organization has already developed a consumer app and is now investing in its merchant-acquiring capabilities to create more value for customers. The Lab in Canada is also where Paytm develops and tests many of its investments in new technologies.
- 8) **Capital and commendations flow:** Paytm's ability to solve problems with technology has made it a darling of technology investors and pundits. The company has won the FT Future of Fintech Award and Forbes' Outstanding Startup of the Year Award. Paytm's founder was featured in Time's 100 Most Influential People (2017) and Harvard Business Review did a case study about Paytm titled, Paytm: Building a Payments Network (2017). China-based Alibaba Group and Japan-based SoftBank have both made significant investments in Paytm over the past 10 years. So, too, have Western investors such as Sapphire Ventures and Berkshire Hathaway. As of the start of last year, the company was valued at more than US\$10 billion.

CHALLENGES OF FINTECH IN INDIA

Fintech companies in spite of having enormous opportunities has still a tough path to walk on. The probable roadblocks of Fintech companies are mentioned herein below:

1. **Stringent Regulatory Framework:** It is very difficult for fintech companies to enter the Indian market due to the stringent regulatory framework which is designed to prevent fraud. This creates a huge barrier for new startups. Before starting its operations, they need to fulfill a lot of legal formalities.
2. **Lack of required infrastructure and other related problems:** The infrastructure of internet connectivity is lacking in many parts of the country. Also, the unbanked population and low literacy levels are among the top hurdles for the fintech companies to work with 100 percent potential. Though Jan Dhan accounts were opened to reduce the unbanked population, the majority of the population prefer cash transactions rather than online transaction because the majority of them do not have smart phones and many hesitate to do online transactions.
3. **Conservative Approach:** Merchants and other users deal with cash transactions for many years, so it is very difficult to change the conservative approach because it is very difficult to change their habits suddenly and shift them to online transactions.
4. **Fraudulent activities:** We often read in newspapers that fraudsters loot the money of innocent persons by using technology. This has been a great challenge for the fintech companies.
5. **Difficult to gain investors' trust:** It is very difficult for fintech companies to gain investors' trust as is happening in another type of industries. It is very difficult for the fintech companies to get seed capital and other required investment from investors, and this leads to negative on the operations and functioning of the fintech companies.

SUGGESTIONS FOR FINTECH

The suggestions for the growth of fintech companies in India are highlighted herein below:

1. **Higher personalization:** Huge customer database can be effectively and efficiently used in providing personalized services (offerings) as per the tastes and preferences of the customers.
2. **Increased speed of service:** Many persons experience delays in completing online transactions. Excess delays are resulting in customer turn-off. So the speed of the service has to be increased to have a good experience for the customers.

3. **Improved convenience:** Fintech companies must make an attempt to make available 24/7 services in order to provide access to any time service at any place through any device or channel.
4. **Better functionality:** Fintech companies must try to keep on improving their services while solving the customers pain points. This will lead to development of innovative solutions.
5. **Proactive insights:** Fintech companies must try to find out the needs of customers in advance i.e., predictive analytics and thus provide financial services accordingly.
6. **Prevention of fraud:** Fintech companies must make an attempt to prevent fraud as well as help customers in creating money saving opportunities.

The above attempts will definitely add appreciation and delight to the customer experience.

CONCLUSIONS

From the above findings, it is concluded that there is huge scope of FinTech in India as less number of users of FinTech are there as of now and people like to access financial service through mobile. Customers are interested in using FinTech services like robo advisors and online lending. Fintech should work on these services where other financial services are not up to the mark. Fast services, easy accessibility and cheap service are the major factors contributing to use of FinTech by customers. People who work in the informal economy or in rural areas have pretty much the same financial services needs as everyone else. But they are often left out of the system because they are not on anyone's radar. Fintech companies understand their need and act accordingly.

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